

RDM for Big Data

Challenge

Data volumes and rates are increasing - instant filtering or selection, making use of AI, is required.

Impact on RDM

Filtering or trigger conditions need to be documented in the metadata.

Dynamic life cycle

The filtering process is not static but dynamic - the outcome influences the filter.

Dynamic archives

... should give the opportunity to re-investigate archival data guided by the available metadata.

Fact sheet

- Time-domain astronomy: observations may be unique and can not simply be repeated. Filtering of data is therefore a sensitive process.
- With respect to sustainable science and Green Computing, data reduction is a crucial step.
- Heßling, H., Kramer, M., and Wagner, S. Next-generation Green Computing. EGI Conference 2021. <https://indico.egi.eu/event/5464/contributions/15661>
- Eatough, R.P., et al. Selection of radio pulsar candidates using artificial neural networks. MNRAS 407 (2010).
<https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2010MNRAS.407.2443E/abstract>
- Balakrishnan, V., et al. Pulsar candidate identification using semi-supervised generative adversarial networks. MNRAS 505 (2021).
<https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2021MNRAS.505.1180B/abstract>
- Ronchetti, R., et al. Efficient high performance computing with the ALICE event processing nodes GPU-based farm. Front. Phys. 13 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2025.1541854>
- Redelbach, A., et al. Curation and metadata - concepts for data irreversibility (Version v1). Zenodo (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10692169>
- Redelbach, A. Specifying the concept of a Dynamic Archive
<https://results.punch4nfdi.de/files/documents/report-D-TA5-WP3-1.pdf>

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